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Research Article

**COMPARATIVE RESEARCH TO COMPARE THE OUTCOMES
AMONG PATIENTS EXPERIENCING TOTAL
THYROIDECTOMY AND SUB-TOTAL THYROIDECTOMY****¹Dr Zarish Fatima Malik, ²Dr. Tayyba Inayat, ³Dr Aneeza Saleem****¹Gujranwala Medical College, ²DHQ Hospital Faisalabad, ³Bhawalpur Victoria Hospital.****Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: The purpose of this research was to compare the outcomes among those patients who underwent total thyroidectomy and sub-total thyroidectomy.

Material and Methods: We carried out this comparative research at Services Hospital, Lahore from March 2017 to January 2018 on a total of 240 patients. All the included patients either underwent total thyroidectomy or they received subtotal thyroidectomy. We also evaluated postoperative hypocalcemia outcomes in all the patients. In this research, we included both female and male patients in the age bracket of 14 – 50 years. We did not include any patient with hypocalcemia due to systemic disease, renal disease, preoperative lactation, postoperative lactation or any other associated disease along with symptomatic postoperative hypocalcemia after total following total thyroidectomy or subtotal thyroidectomy.

Results: Patients were divided in Group – I & II with a respective mean age of (30.94 ± 9.6) years and (31.59 ± 11.03) years. In the total population 62 patients (35.63%) presented asymptomatic hypocalcemia in Group – I and 30 patients (17.24%) in Group – II. Significant statistical difference between both groups was present with a P-Value of (0.00).

Conclusion: There was a significant increase in the occurrence of asymptomatic hypocalcemia after experiencing total thyroidectomy than sub-total thyroidectomy. Asymptomatic hypocalcemia affects both male and female equally either after receiving total thyroidectomy or after undergoing subtotal thyroidectomy. Both young and old age is under the same risk of development of asymptomatic hypocalcemia after total thyroidectomy or subtotal thyroidectomy.

Key Words: FNAC, MNG, Thyroid Isotope Scan, HPE, Thyrotoxicosis, Total Thyroidectomy and Subtotal Thyroidectomy.

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INTRODUCTION:

Thyroidectomy is among frequently repeated procedure with 0.33% to 65% complication of postoperative hypocalcemia [1]. Clinical and biochemical methods prove the evidence of hypocalcemia in both total thyroidectomy and subtotal thyroidectomy. Hypocalcemia comes with symptomatic symptoms of carpedal spasms, facial muscles twitching, even seizures and irritability; whereas, it can also be totally asymptomatic [2 – 5]. Patients face the miserable state in the immediate postoperative time and may pose a permanent issue. We need to carefully observe the biochemical and clinical profile of the patients. This careful observation is helpful to reduce the rate of mortality and morbidity among patients of thyroidectomy. The frequency of temporary hypocalcemia ranges from 1.60% to 50.00% after the surgery of the thyroid and the occurrence of permanent hypocalcemia is about 1.50% to 4.00% of the total surgeries [6]. There are different causes of hypocalcemia which include increased excretion of urinary calcium which is secondary to surgical stress, hemodilution which is secondary to intravenous administration of fluid in the course of perioperative phase, hungry bone syndrome among metabolic bone disease patients and release of calcitonin after manipulation of the thyroid gland [7]. However, hypoparathyroidism through the removal of parathyroid, devascularization of parathyroid glands or direct injury is likely to be the major reason of postoperative hypocalcemia [7]. Acute hypocalcemia and severe hypocalcemia are medical emergencies which requires an immediate remedial action. Hospitalization is prolonged due to hypocalcemia. Unnecessary hospital stay may be reduced with an in-time detection of the lower level of calcium [8]. Hypocalcemia symptoms become evident in case of a reduced level of serum under 8 mg/dl; whereas, the normal range is (8.5 mg/dl – 10.5 mg/dl) [8]. An immediate decrease in the level of calcium serum after surgery is a sensitive marker for clinical hypocalcemia [9]. Immediate treatment is necessary for the management of hypocalcemia among thyroidectomy patients. The purpose of this research was to compare the outcomes among those patients who underwent total thyroidectomy and sub-total thyroidectomy.

Asymptomatic Hypocalcemia refers to the level of calcium < 2 mmol/l (8 mg/dl) not presenting clinical symptoms and hypocalcemia symptoms after twenty-four hours postoperatively.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We carried out this comparative research at Services Hospital, Lahore from March 2017 to January 2018 on a total of 240 patients. All the included patients either underwent total thyroidectomy or they received subtotal thyroidectomy. We also evaluated postoperative hypocalcemia outcomes in all the patients. In this research, we included both female and male patients in the age bracket of 14 – 50 years. We did not include any patient with hypocalcemia due to systemic disease, renal disease, preoperative lactation, postoperative lactation or any other associated disease along with symptomatic postoperative hypocalcemia after total following total thyroidectomy or subtotal thyroidectomy. Patients were included after meeting the inclusion criteria set for the research. Patients also gave their informed written consent for participation. Ethical permission was also sought from ERB of the institution before research commencement. Patients were divided into two groups through the lottery method. Group A and B respectively included those patients who underwent total and subtotal thyroidectomy. Clinical assessment was made for the level of calcium serum before twenty-four hours of surgery. Detailed demographic information about surgery type, gender and age was also taken from the patients. Statistical analysis was made through the Chi-Square Test and SPSS (P-Value \leq 0.05).

RESULTS:

Patients were divided in Group – I & II with a respective mean age of (30.94 \pm 9.6) years and (31.59 \pm 11.03) years. In the total population 62 patients (35.63%) presented asymptomatic hypocalcemia in Group – I and 30 patients (17.24%) in Group – II. Overall mean age was (31.27 \pm 10.33) years. In Group – A, 120 patients underwent total thyroidectomy and among these patients, 45 presented asymptomatic hypocalcemia (37.5%). In Group – B, 120 patients underwent sub-total thyroidectomy and among these patients, 19 presented asymptomatic hypocalcemia (15.83%). Significant statistical difference between both groups was present with a P-Value of (0.00). Stratification with respect to the gender of both groups was done. There were 38 males in Group – A, among these patients 18 presented asymptomatic hypocalcemia; whereas, Group – B included 41 males, among which 7 presented asymptomatic hypocalcemia (17.07%). Detailed outcomes of comparison of asymptomatic hypocalcemia are given in Table – I, gender-wise comparison of asymptomatic hypocalcemia is given in Table – II and age-wise comparison of asymptomatic hypocalcemia are given in Table – III.

Table – I: Comparison of Asymptomatic Hypocalcemia

Asymptomatic Hypocalcemia	Yes		No		P-Value
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Group – I	45	37.5	75	62.5	0.001
Group – II	19	15.83	101	84.17	

Table – II: Gender-Wise Comparison of Asymptomatic Hypocalcemia

Asymptomatic Hypocalcemia		Yes		No		Total	P-Value
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage		
Male	Group – I	18	47.37	20	52.63	38	0.007
	Group – II	7	17.07	34	82.93		
Female	Group – I	32	39.02	50	60.98	82	0.010
	Group – II	16	20.25	63	79.75		

Table – III: Age-Wise Comparison of Asymptomatic Hypocalcemia

Asymptomatic Hypocalcemia		Yes		No		Total	P-Value
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage		
18 – 32 Years	Group – I	27	37.5	45	62.5	72	0.015
	Group – II	13	18.58	57	81.42	70	
33 – 50 Years	Group – I	16	33.33	32	66.67	48	0.032
	Group – II	7	14	43	86	50	

DISCUSSION:

Multiple factors are responsible for post-thyroidectomy hypocalcemia development. There are different causes of hypocalcemia which include increased excretion of urinary calcium which is secondary to surgical stress, hemodilution which is secondary to intravenous administration of fluid in the course of perioperative phase, hungry bone syndrome among metabolic bone disease patients and release of calcitonin after manipulation of the thyroid gland. However, hypoparathyroidism through the removal of parathyroid, devascularization of parathyroid glands or direct injury is likely to be the major reason for postoperative hypocalcemia [10].

The occurrence of asymptomatic hypocalcemia was more in Group – A than Group – B (37.5% versus 15.83%). Islam treated 65 patients of total thyroidectomy irrespective of sex and age among which occurrence rate was 88% about asymptomatic hypocalcemia [11]. These outcomes are higher than our reported outcomes. According to Iqbal, the occurrence rate was 24.14% about asymptomatic

hypocalcemia [12]. Every patient experienced total thyroidectomy and the outcomes of our research cannot be compared with this study. Erbil studied 130 patients with asymptomatic hypocalcemia and multinodular goitre and reported 31.2% of cases [13]. Various other authors also presented different occurrence rates in their respective series [14 – 17]. Our reported asymptomatic hypocalcemia among male population of Group – A was 47.37% and 17.07% in Group – B; whereas, asymptomatic hypocalcemia among female population of Group – A was 39.02% and 20.25% in Group – B. Díez reported the occurrence of asymptomatic hypocalcemia in males and females with respective proportions of 21.4% and 35.8% [18]. The outcomes presented by Díez are inconsistent with our outcomes. We reported significant variation in old and young age for post thyroidectomy asymptomatic hypocalcemia (P-Value = 0.015). Another study reported a significantly increased rate of asymptomatic hypocalcemia among old aged patients which was carried out on 34 patients with 41.2% incidence of asymptomatic hypocalcemia [19].

CONCLUSION:

There was a significant increase in the occurrence of asymptomatic hypocalcemia after experiencing total thyroidectomy than sub-total thyroidectomy. Asymptomatic hypocalcemia affects both male and female equally either after receiving total thyroidectomy or after undergoing subtotal thyroidectomy. Both young and old age is under the same risk of development of asymptomatic hypocalcemia after total thyroidectomy or subtotal thyroidectomy.

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